

A RESEARCH PROJECT

ON

**AWARENESS ON RISK FACTORS OF AND PREVENTIVE PRACTICES AGAINST
CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES AMONG HEALTHCARE WORKERS IN THE
UNIVERSITY OF UYO TEACHING HOSPITAL, UYO, AKWA IBOM STATE.**

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION: Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are a spectrum of heart and blood vessel disorders that potentially affect health. They include but are not limited to ischemic heart disease, coronary artery disease, hypertensive heart disease, cardiomyopathies and valvular heart diseases like rheumatic heart disease. CVDs are the leading cause of mortality worldwide and are a major contributor to the prevalence of NCDs globally. In recent times, there has been a progressive increase in the prevalence of CVDs in the Sub-Saharan African region which can be attributed to the adoption of Western lifestyles. Age, black race and a positive family history are non-modifiable risk factors for CVDs. Modifiable risk factors for CVDs include hypertension, sedentary lifestyle, obesity, smoking, alcohol abuse, and a low fibre diet. Studies to assess the awareness of risk factors and adoption of preventive practices are ubiquitous in medical literature. However, these studies are mostly focused on other non-medical workers. Existing studies have shown a relatively good level of knowledge among Healthcare workers compared to other populations but this does not always translate to engagement in preventive practices. Previous studies have identified factors like cultural beliefs, environmental factors, long working hours associated with the medical profession as possible reasons for this trend.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES: This study aims to provide an objective assessment of the awareness of cardiovascular risk factors, the engagement in preventive practices and describe any factors associated with the knowledge of and preventive practices against cardiovascular diseases amongst Healthcare workers in the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital (UUTH). UUTH is a tertiary hospital in Uyo, the capital of Akwa Ibom state with 1967 Health Care workers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: A descriptive cross-sectional study will be used for this study. Respondents will include doctors, nurses, medical laboratory scientists, pharmacists, dieticians and medical social workers currently employed in UUTH. Sample size will be determined using Cochran's 1977 formula for cross-sectional studies. Our calculated sample size is 295. A finite sample size will be determined for each category of Healthcare workers using proportional allocation. Members of each category will be recruited into the study using serial enrollment. Analysis of the data will be done using the SPSS software. The study tool which is a semi-structured questionnaire designed by the researchers will be interviewer-administered and will comprise 78 questions. It will be pre-tested in St Luke's Hospital, Anua and validated. Data will be entered, cleaned and analyzed using SPSS version 20 software.

CONCLUSION: In conclusion, it is expected that the result of this study will add to the pool of knowledge on the awareness of cardiovascular risk factors amongst doctors as well as the preventive practices used by doctors against cardiovascular diseases which may help in policy framing on establishing NCD preventive measures in health facilities in the State.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are a group of disorders of the heart and blood vessels and include coronary heart disease, hypertension, heart failure, cerebrovascular disease, arrhythmias, rheumatic heart disease and other valvular heart diseases, peripheral artery disease and congenital heart defects.¹ More than four out of five CVD deaths are due to heart attacks and strokes, and one third of these deaths occur prematurely in people under 70 years of age.¹ In Sub-Saharan Africa, CVDs account for approximately 13% of all deaths and 37% of all NCD deaths making it the highest contributor to NCD-related mortality in the region.² In Nigeria, CVDs account for 11% of over 2 million NCD deaths annually.³

According to the Global Burden of Diseases (GBD) study in 2022, the leading risk factors for CVDs are categorized into - metabolic, behavioural and environmental. These are high systolic blood pressure, high low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C), high body mass index (BMI), high fasting plasma glucose, kidney dysfunction, diet, tobacco smoking; including secondhand tobacco smoke, alcohol abuse, and low physical activity.⁴ Others include - ambient particulate matter air pollution, household air pollution from solid fuels, exposure to lead, and low or high temperature.⁴ Amongst these, high systolic blood pressure remains the leading modifiable risk factor globally for premature cardiovascular deaths. In 2021, hypertension accounted for 10.8 million cardiovascular deaths and 11.3 million deaths overall.⁵ It and has been particularly linked to ischemic heart disease and stroke-related deaths.

An effective plan by the American Heart Association summarizes preventive strategies against CVDs into seven health behaviours. These are:- cessation of smoking, maintaining a healthy

body mass index, achieving appropriate levels of physical activity, achieving a healthy diet (more fruits, vegetables, whole grains, polyunsaturated fats as opposed to and low-fibre diet, refined sugars and trans-fats), maintaining a total cholesterol of <200 mg/dL, maintaining a blood pressure of <120/80 mm Hg, and a maintaining a fasting glucose of <100 mg/dL.⁶

The prevalence of cardiovascular disorders among healthcare workers have been increasing in the past few years and research have identified various risk factors that affect cardiovascular health: like shift work, high stress, anxiety, work environment, obesity, high basal metabolic index, and others.⁷ Even though health care providers are aware of the need of addressing their health issues their actions are either absent or too delayed to be construed as conscious decisions regarding their own health.⁷ Studies conducted at the University of Ebonyi Teaching Hospital revealed that 37% of Health Care Workers (HCWs) do not meet the minimum level of physical activity in a week⁸ and the feeding behaviours of health care workers were considered 'inadequate' for good health.⁹ Another study revealed that most medical doctors were poor sleepers with majority sleeping for <7 hours in the night. Some of the doctors had worked for up to 5 years.⁹ House officers and medical officers also showed more tendencies for daytime sleepiness.¹⁰

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

CVDs are the leading cause of death globally. An estimated 17.9 million people died from CVDs in 2019, representing 32% of all global deaths. Of these deaths, 85% were due to heart attack and stroke.¹ Out of the 17 million premature deaths (under the age of 70) due to non-Communicable diseases in 2019, 38% were caused by CVDs globally.¹ In 2019, more than 1 million deaths were attributable to CVDs in Sub-Saharan Africa, which constituted 5.4 % of all global CVD-related deaths, and 13% of all deaths in Africa.¹¹ According to Dr. Nnenna

Ezeigwe, the National Coordinator for NCDs in the Nigerian Federal Ministry of Health (FMoH), “CVD is a significant public health concern responsible for 11% of over 2 million NCD deaths in Nigeria annually. It is also responsible for a high burden of morbidity and disability.³ In 2023, the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital (UUTH) in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, had an overall prevalence of 30.1% of Hypertension among patients attending the General outpatient department (GOPD).¹²

The burden of CVDs is further compounded by a lack of implementation of preventive strategies. A study amongst Health Care Workers in India showed that 79% of men and 83% of women were physically inactive, 48% of women and 51% of men consumed high-fat diet, 57% of women and 60% of men consumed fruits and vegetables in low quantity.¹³ Furthermore, 0.5% of women and 12% of men smoked tobacco.¹³ In this study amongst Indian Healthcare Workers, it was also found that 49.2% of doctors had a high risk of CVDs; 42.1% of doctors were physically inactive; 19.8% of all doctors had unfavourable dietary patterns in Medical college hospital, Tamil Nadu.¹³ At the Delta State University Teaching Hospital, the prevalence rate of Hypertension among Healthcare Professionals was 36.2%. Three quarters (75%) of these patients had a family history of hypertension. In this population, there was a significant relationship between obesity and hypertension with an odds ratio of 2.13 (CI 1.20-3.80).¹⁴

The most feared complication from CVD is death.¹⁵ Despite multiple discoveries aimed at its control, CVDs remain among the leading causes of death all over the world owing to their alarming prevalence in the populations.¹⁵ Other complications such as the need for longer hospitalizations, physical disability, and increased costs of care, are significant and are the focus for health-care policymakers as it is believed they will continue to increase in the coming decades. For people with heart failure with reduced ejection fraction (HFrEF) of less than

35%, as the risk of life-threatening arrhythmias is exceedingly high in these patients, current guidelines recommend the use of an implantable-cardioverter defibrillator (ICD) for those with symptoms equivalent to a New York Heart Association (NYHA) Class II-IV, despite maximal tolerated medical therapy.¹⁵ Strokes can leave people with severe disabling sequelae like dysarthria or aphasia, dysphagia, focal or generalized muscle weakness or paresis that can be temporary or cause permanent physical disability that may lead to a complete bedbound state, due to hemiplegia with added complications secondary to immobility, as is the higher risk of developing urinary tract infections and/or risk for thromboembolic events.¹⁵ There is an increased risk of all-cause death for people with Peripheral Arterial Disease (PAD) compared to those without evidence of peripheral disease. Chronic wounds, physical limitation, and limb ischemia are among other complications from PAD.¹⁵

1.3 JUSTIFICATION

Despite their role in improving health, healthcare workers are not exempted from the risk factors associated with CVDs. Some of the major risk factors for CVDs like physical inactivity, sleep deprivation, chronic exhaustion caused by work stress or burnout can be identified in this cohort. This affects not only their health, but may also affect the quality of medical care,¹⁶ which may lead to poor health outcomes. Most cardiovascular diseases can be prevented by addressing behavioural risk factors such as tobacco use, unhealthy diet, obesity, physical inactivity and harmful use of alcohol.⁷ Therefore, the burden of these diseases can be mitigated through increased awareness and implementation of preventive practices. It should be emphasized that awareness alone is insufficient as knowledge does not always translate into practice. This study will identify any existing knowledge-practice gap amongst health care workers and reveal whether they practice what they teach. The resultant effect is a likely increase in both consciousness and effort in carrying out preventive practices against CVDs.

This study has the potential of influencing the work schedule of healthcare workers by adjusting it to suit their health needs and produce better outcome in patient management. For instance, a study investigated the impact of shift work on the health of nurses. Since the nursing profession requires providing care to the patients 24 hours, shift work is usually practiced in most healthcare facilities across the world. The study found that shift work affects the psychophysical homeostasis of nurses and acts as a risk factor for metabolic disorders, cardiovascular disorders, sleep disorders, diabetes and stress. Thus, the high stress environment of the nursing profession results in cardiovascular disorders, of which hypertension is the most common.⁷

The body of knowledge amongst the different levels of health care workers is not equal. This study will gauge the level of awareness amongst different health care workers. Evidence from this study will be useful in the development of policy guidelines in the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital, with respect to the provision of comprehensive care for health workers. Understanding the influences and preventive strategies against cardiovascular diseases within a local context, in this case, amongst Health Care Workers in the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital could contribute to more effective, context-specific interventions and policies.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What proportion of HCWs in UUTH have a good knowledge of the risk factors of common CVDs (coronary heart disease, hypertension, heart failure, cerebrovascular disease, arrhythmias, rheumatic heart disease)?
2. What proportion of healthcare workers in the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital use preventive practices, such as adopting healthier lifestyles, to mitigate their risk of CVDs?
3. What factors are associated with the implementation of these preventive practices among healthcare workers in the University Uyo Teaching Hospital?

1.4 GENERAL OBJECTIVES

This study seeks to assess the awareness level and implementation of preventive practices of cardiovascular disease (CVD) risk factors among healthcare workers at the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital. This research aims to contribute to an in-depth understanding of the factors that influence the healthcare workers' knowledge and preventive practices, thereby providing valuable insight to guide future interventions and policies.

1.5 SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

1. To determine the proportion of HCWs in UUTH that have a good knowledge of the risk factors of common CVDs (coronary heart disease, hypertension, heart failure, cerebrovascular disease, arrhythmias, rheumatic heart disease).
2. To determine the proportion of HCWs engaged in preventive practices against CVDs in UUTH.
3. To describe factors that are associated with the implementation of preventive practices among HCWs in UUTH.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

An electronic search was done using Chrome, Opera Mini and UC Browser. The keywords used were: Cardiovascular diseases, Healthcare workers, Risk factors of cardiovascular diseases, Preventive practices against cardiovascular diseases, Knowledge-practice gap. The sites where related articles and publications were found include PubMed Central, PubMed, Google Scholar, Academia.edu, Elsevier. The search was not limited to any duration. However, preferred references were articles or publications within the last 5 years.

2.1 Epidemiology of Cardiovascular Disease

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are the leading cause of global morbidity and a major contributor to disability.¹⁷ As of 2019, CVDs accounted for an estimated 17.9 million deaths, representing 32% of all global deaths. In 2021, there was an estimated 14% increase to 20.5 million deaths representing a third of all deaths globally.¹⁷ While CVD deaths have increased overall in the last three decades, globally, the age-standardized death rate has fallen indicating that some progress is being made.¹⁷ However, a closer look at the data reveals this progress is uneven and is beginning to stall. The decline in death rates for CVDs has been much faster in High-Income countries (HICs) compared to low- and middle income countries (LMICs), where more than 80% of CVD deaths occur globally.¹⁷ In addition to disparities between countries, inequalities in cardiovascular outcomes within countries is also staggering, with research showing disparities according to sex, ethnicity and socioeconomic status, among other.¹⁷

Ischaemic heart disease is the leading cause of CVD mortality in both males and females. However, for both sexes in South Asia, and for females in Sub-Saharan Africa, stroke is the leading cause of CVD mortality.¹⁷ Stroke is on average the second leading cause of CVD

mortality across regions.¹⁷ Up to 80% of premature heart attacks and strokes can be prevented, but morbidity and mortality from CVDs continue to rise because the tools that can help diagnose, prevent, and treat CVDs are not benefitting the communities who need them most.¹⁷ Although around 4 in every 5 CVD deaths occur in low- and middle-income countries, progress in cardiovascular health is increasingly concentrated in high-income countries, thereby perpetuating the gap of health inequities globally.¹⁷

A study in India revealed that a doctor is more than twice as likely to develop CVD or Stroke than the general population.¹⁸ In Sarawak, Malaysia, a study amongst health care workers revealed that 5.3% of these workers identified as having underlying hypertension, dyslipidemia and/or diabetes mellitus. More than half (58.1%) of the healthcare workers were classified as having an intermediate risk for CVD. The unhealthy category covered 3.4% of these workers. In the aforementioned population, almost half of the healthcare workers were overweight to obese (47.4%).¹⁹ A study conducted in Cameroon revealed that the highest number of CVDs in HCWs occur between the ages of 30-39, with nurses having more CVDs than others.²⁰ In North Central Nigeria, the 10-year risk of developing cardiovascular disease among the health workers using the Framingham risk score was 0.7% for high risk, 1.0% for moderate risk, while 98.3% had low risk.²¹

2.2 Prevalence of Risk Factors of Cardiovascular Disease among Health Care workers

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) affect the heart or blood vessels and involve a combination of socio-economic, metabolic, behavioral, and environmental risk factors. These include high blood pressure, unhealthy diet, high cholesterol, diabetes, air pollution, obesity, tobacco use, kidney disease, physical inactivity, harmful use of alcohol and stress.¹⁷ In 2021, according to the Global Burden of Disease Study, high blood pressure was the leading modifiable risk factor globally for mortality and contributed to 10.8 million CVD deaths worldwide.

In a study conducted in Turkey by Gopal et al, 52.4% of health care workers had high blood pressure and all the participants have high body fat percentage with body mass index as overweight.²² A study in Sefwi-Wiawso Municipal Hospital, Ghana showed that the prevalence of hypertension was 16.07% and 52.68% respectively. About 38.39% of participants were overweight, and 12.5% were obese. Prevalence of atherogenic dyslipidemia was 26.79%, and 4.5% of these healthcare workers were diabetic.²³ A study conducted over a period of 20 years revealed that nurses and doctors in Brazil experienced excessive weight gain as well as increased the prevalence of the systemic arterial hypertension. The study revealed high prevalence of the dyslipidemia in the healthcare professionals along with an excess alcohol consumption among the nursing professionals. In Singapore another study was carried out for estimating the occurrence of modifiable risk factors related to CVDs among health providers as well as non-health workers and it was found that around 10% of the nurses and doctors had dyslipidemia, with 7% being obese that is more than 30 kg/m² body mass index.⁷

There is a paucity of recent studies concerning cardiovascular risk factors among Nigerian Health care workers. However, in a study amongst Nigerian Healthcare workers in Bayelsa, over half were either overweight or obese.²⁴ Almost half (49.1%) of the participants had low level of physical activity with only 11% having high physical activity level. Respondents had BP in pre-hypertensive (48.2%), stage 1 (18.5%), or stage 2 hypertension (3.6%) ranges, only 7.7% had a previous diagnosis of hypertension. Only 25.4% took fruits on a daily basis and engaged in aerobic exercises up to 30 minutes daily or at least 3–5 times a week. Other poor lifestyle choices included non-lean meat intake (76.8%), low water intake (88.2%), and junk food and soda drinks intake (daily 28%, weekly 51.2%). Up to one third of respondents took alcohol in a range of 1–50 units weekly with a mean of 7.25±8.59 units weekly. According to this study, low levels of aerobic activity among physicians were due to the rigors of medical

training and the residency programs that are very stressful and leave medical students and residency trainees little time and incentive to eat healthy and be physically active. Daily intake of junk foods and soda drinks as found among 28% of study participants in this study is associated with increased risk of obesity, hypertension, and CVDs such as stroke, heart failure, and ischemic heart disease. In the same study, while respondents had BP in prehypertensive (48.2%), stage 1 (18.5%), or stage 2 hypertension (3.6%) ranges, only 7.7% had a previous diagnosis of hypertension. Only 25.4% took fruits on a daily basis and engaged in aerobic exercises up to 30 minutes daily or at least 3–5 times a week. Other poor lifestyle choices included non-lean meat intake (76.8%), low water intake (88.2%), and junk food and soda drinks intake (daily 28%, weekly 51.2%).²⁴

In a study done in a sample of employees at a higher education institution in Portugal, it showed that most participants (69.5%) do not walk over 30 min/day as recommended by the WHO, and more than half of the participants (58.3%) do not practice any type of regular physical activity. Nearly one-third of this population walks less than 15 min a day and about a fifth has sedentary behaviour.²⁵ A study done among staff of Ekiti State University, Ado Ekiti, Nigeria, low knowledge of heart disease risk factors was found in 68.6% of the respondents. The prevalence of hypertension, diabetes mellitus, overweight, obesity, physical inactivity was 35.4%, 12.1%, 31.8%, 23.3%, and 83% respectively. Family history of hypertension was a predictor of a high level of knowledge.²⁶

In a study done among the staff of college of health science, the study participants demonstrated moderate-to-high stress (48%), physical inactivity of 18.9%, overweight/obesity of 62.48%, abdominal obesity of 21.4%, hypertensive (systole and diastole) of 27.2%, hyperglycemic of 7.2%, and smokers of 7.2%.²⁷ In a community based survey, they were predominantly farmers, petty traders and artisans. The identified CVD risk factors were hypertension 285 (26.4%),

alcohol abuse 131 (12.1%), obesity 122 (11.3%), diabetes 97 (9%), family history of stroke 87 (8.1%), smoking 74 (6.9%) and previous stroke 29 (2.7%).²⁸ A study done among company workers in Rivers State, Nigeria showed 64.9% of the respondents were married and 59.5% were male. 52.0% drank alcohol, and 7.4% smoked. While 67.2% claimed they were not hypertensive, 22.6% don't know their blood pressure status, and 58.1% were physically inactive. The prevalence of hypertension was 33.4%, and the prevalence of overweight and obesity was 43.6% and 15.2%, respectively²⁹

2.3 Knowledge of Cardiovascular Risk factors and Engagement in Preventive Practices Amongst Health Care Workers

Despite easy access to Healthcare facilities and firsthand knowledge, many doctors were found to be unaware of their own blood pressure and cholesterol levels indicating that awareness does not automatically translate to correction of risk factors.¹⁸ In a study amongst Healthcare workers in Diyala Governate, Baghdad, results showed that most of health care workers had responded at a Good level of knowledge on risk factors (87.5%). Results regarding practice observed that most of health care workers had responded at a Good level of practice with only (7.14%) having a poor evaluation only. Most participants strongly agreed to exercising more than 20 minutes about 3 times a week, maintaining normal weight, stress management, quitting smoking, taking omega-3 fatty acids for heart disease prevention, while the majority of participants strongly disagreed to adding salt to food randomly. These findings indicated good practice amongst health care workers in Baghdad. Most health care professionals showed an appropriate level of physical activity.³⁰ In another study, men performed more transport-related and health-enhancing physical activity than women. Younger professionals and those with higher education were more compliant with health-enhancing and muscle-strengthening

physical activity guidelines. Physiotherapists were more physically active when compared to the rest of health care professionals.³¹

In a study conducted amongst Pharmacists in Northwest Ethiopia, of the participants, 45 (55.6%) of them were found knowledgeable about cardiovascular disease. On the other hand, only 18.5%, 77.8%, and 93.8% of the study participants respectively were aware of CVD risk factors like symptoms of heart disease, the connection of family history of heart disease, and the connection between old age and heart disease. Only 21% of the study participants had known the existence of HTN guidelines in Ethiopia. X2 statistical analysis showed that there was no statistically significant association between age ($P = 0.82$), gender ($P = 0.661$). Marital statuses ($P > 0.50$), number of years of practice ($P = 0.796$) and cardiovascular disease.³² Another study conducted amongst Community Pharmacists in Lagos demonstrated that the participants displayed good knowledge of both the behavioural (physical inactivity, smoking and unhealthy diets) and biologic (hypertension, diabetes, obesity and dyslipidemia) risk factors for CVD. However, participants displayed low knowledge of level High Density Lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-c) in diabetes and females with diabetes having a higher risk of development of heart disease. Stroke was correctly identified as an example of a CVD by 73 (47.4%) of the respondents while the same number of respondents wrongly identified hypertension as a CVD. On the other hand 136 (81.4%) of the pharmacists correctly identified smoking as a CVD risk factor. The percentage of those who correctly identified the diagnostic cut-off points for hypertension, obesity with BMI, abdominal obesity were 57.7%, 25.6%, 22.6% respectively.³³

In another study amongst nurses at the University College Hospital, Ibadan, majority demonstrated a high level of awareness about cardiovascular risk factors such as cigarette smoking (78.1%), alcohol use (76.5%), overweight/obese (75.5%), high blood cholesterol

(73.5%), physical inactivity (71.9%) and diabetes mellitus (70.9%). However, there was a low level of awareness about cardiovascular risk factors such as race (41.3%) and gender (34.2%).³⁴ In Southern Nigeria, Medical doctors showed low rates of undergoing routine medical checks on themselves despite possibly dying more from physical illnesses than mental health challenges, which have been the foci of most studies on doctors' health and health-related behaviors. Doctors had a prevalence rate of CVDs of 4%–15% previously reported.²⁴ A study amongst health care workers in Rivers State showed that staff in the medical facilities have a relatively low level of compliance towards prevention of risk factors. It was therefore recommended that health workers should check on a regular basis their blood pressure, sugar and lipid levels and all of them should adopt healthy lifestyle choices including a regular physical activity and a diet of fruits and vegetables.³⁵

Studies also carried out among staff of Ekiti state university shows there were 103 males (46.2%). Low knowledge of heart disease risk factors was found in 68.6% of the respondents.³⁶ In Agro-Allied company in Nigeria, the awareness among workers shows 59.4% of the respondents had high awareness of cardiovascular risk factors. Stress was the most recognized cardiovascular risk factor, followed by hypertension and smoking. Majority of the workers (57.8%) got their information about cardiovascular risk factors from the media.³⁷

2.4 Factors Influencing the Utilization of Preventive Practices Among Health Care Workers

2.4.1. Cultural beliefs

Culture determines our food habits and shapes our beliefs and value systems.³⁸ In spite of the awareness of health care workers in UUTH on the CVD preventive measures, their cultures and beliefs can hinder implementation of the practices. Observational studies indicate that

people owing to their culturally shaped habits do not easily adopt suggestions for lifestyle changes. An Australian study highlighted the unwillingness of participants in adopting fruits and vegetables even though they acknowledged its superiority for cardiovascular health, primarily because of the culturally formed meat-eating habits and the pleasure derived from it.³⁸ Acculturation, defined as the cultural shift resulting from the interaction of two different cultures, due to either immigration or being born to parents belonging to different cultures also affects food habits. For example, diet adaptations in the Arab, Asian and Hispanic immigrants to the USA for highly processed food are extremely harmful to their heart's health.³⁸

In African American and South Asian populations, cultural beliefs such as fatalism, collectivism and traditional gender roles clashed with dietary adherence. Traditional beliefs and ideas, collectivism, family and kinship ties, fatalism, cultural norms and normative thinking played critical roles in medication adherence and use of complementary/alternative medicine.³⁹ Culturally influenced mistrust of modern medicine is a significant barrier to both initiation and persistence in adherence to CVD medication and preventive practices among health care workers. A qualitative analysis of the ethno-cultural drivers of non-adherence in South-Asian cardiac patients identified distrust of the western healthcare system as the major reason for non-adherence. Patients of South Asian and Chinese ethnicity were also more anxious about the long-term effect of the prescribed medicines.³⁸ Alternative medicines include using herbal products from Chinese or Ayurvedic medicine and following health practices like acupuncture, yoga, energy therapies, etc. A Canadian study reported lower adherence to anti-hypertension medication and preventive practices among Chinese immigrants chiefly due to belief in traditional Chinese herbs and a perception of lower benefits of western medications.³⁸

2.4.2. Environmental Factors

A shift from rural to urban households can impact on the nutritional quotient of the food eaten. Food preparation from fresh seasonal ingredients is healthy and is a norm in rural cuisines; however, urban households rely on the unhealthier processed and frozen ingredients for the sake of reducing preparation time.⁴⁰ People in cold climates people tend to smoke more. When weather is extremely cold, a one unit increase in temperature (in Fahrenheit scale) leads to one more cigarette smoked per month by a smoker. However, when the weather is extremely hot, a one unit increase in temperature leads to 2.5 less cigarette smoked per month by a smoker.⁴¹

2.4.3. Lack of Awareness

According to a study among Primary Care physicians in the West region of Cameroon, greater than 50% of doctors were not aware of their own risk profile for cardiovascular diseases.⁴² One of the challenges of HCWs' engagement in preventive practices is the need for access to continuous education and training in CVD prevention. Continuous learning is crucial for HCWs to remain current on the latest research and guidelines related to CVD prevention and to communicate this information effectively to patients as well indulge in the practice themselves. Overcoming this challenge might involve creating tailored training programs and providing resources to support lifelong learning.⁴²

2.4.4. Long working hours

The Nigerian Journal of Clinical Practice states that the mean duty hours of Nigerian Doctors is 107 hours per week. This value is higher than the duty hours reported in other African and Non-African countries.⁴³ According to the WHO working 55 or more hours per week is associated with an estimated 35% higher risk of a stroke and a 17% higher risk of dying from ischemic heart disease, compared to working 35-40 hours a week.⁴⁴

2.4.5. Socioeconomic status

Socioeconomic status (SES) has a measurable and significant effect on cardiovascular health as well its prevention of the disease. The following socioeconomic measures have been consistently associated with CVD income level, educational attainment and employment status. Low SES has been linked to the development of CVD as well as an hindrance to the implementation of the preventive measures against the disease.mechanisms.⁴⁵ A study by Woodward et al analyzed nearly 90 000 individuals in Australia and New Zealand and found that those with a primary education had an increased risk of CVD, cardiovascular mortality, and all-cause mortality in comparison with individuals with a tertiary education.⁴⁵ Gerber et al found that each \$10 000 increase in median income of a neighborhood reduced mortality risk in the group by 10%.⁴⁵

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 STUDY AREA

This Study will be carried out in the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Akwa Ibom State is one of the 36 states in Nigeria, it is located in coastal southern part of the country positioned between Latitudes 4°32'N and 5°33'N, and Longitudes 7°25'E and 8°25'E. It occupies a land mass of approximately 7,249 square kilometers in area. The state is located in the South-South geopolitical zone with Cross River State forming the eastern border, Rivers and Abia states on the west with the Atlantic Ocean and the Southern-most part of Cross River forming the southern border. It consist of 31 local government areas, and has a population of about 3,902,051 from the 2006 census. According to the Nigerian population growth rate socio-demographic characteristics, the growth rate of the state showed an annual increase of 3.4%, thus bringing the 2023 estimated population to about 7,200,000.

Akwa Ibom has a rich culture as evidenced by its diversity in arts and crafts, music, dressing, festival, dance and hospitality of the people. The main languages spoken in addition to English Language include Ibibio, Annang, Oro with minor differences in dialect. Their dominant religion is Christianity; there is freedom of worship.

Uyo is a local government area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria as well as the state capital. It has an area of 187km² with an estimated population of 1,200,000. Within it are several health institutions ranging from private, public, primary, secondary and tertiary health facilities.

University of Uyo Teaching Hospital was established in 1999 as Federal Medical center but was renamed as University of Uyo Teaching Hospital in 2008. It is the only tertiary health facility in Akwa Ibom State with a 500 bed capacity and located along Abak Road in Uyo. The hospital offers maternity, radiologic, surgical, emergency and other services to the general

public. It serves as a major referral center for other hospitals within Uyo and surrounding areas. Also, it functions as a training facility for Undergraduates, Residents and Post-graduate doctors. There are many consultants in the departments, nurses, medical laboratory scientists, physiotherapist and other paramedics who work together in making sure the hospital responds to every health need of the society.

3.2 STUDY DESIGN

A descriptive cross-sectional study design will be used to achieve the objectives of this study which will be conducted from October 2023 to December 2023.

3.3 STUDY POPULATION

The study will involve healthcare workers (Doctors, Nurses, pharmacists, laboratory scientists and physiotherapists, dieticians and medical social workers) in the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

S/N	Categories of HCWs	Number of HCWs
1	Medical Doctors	277
2	Nurses	534
3	Medical Laboratory Scientists	7
4	Pharmacists	39
5	Physiotherapists	17
6	Dieticians	8
7	Medical Social workers	5

Table 1.1 showing the number of healthcare providers in the various cadres.

(This table was adapted from the Health Information Management Department, UUTH)

3.4 INCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Health care workers in the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.
2. Health care workers who are in direct delivery of health care services such as doctors, nurses, pharmacists, laboratory technologists, radiographers, dentists, optometrists, community health officers, community health extension workers, etc.

3.5 EXCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Health care workers in the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital, Uyo, who are on leave at the time of this study.
2. Healthcare workers in the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital, Uyo who are absent from work at the time of this study.
3. Health care workers in the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital, Uyo who did not consent to be part of this study.

3.6 SAMPLE SIZE DETERMINATION

The Sample size of this study is determined using Cochran's 1977 formula of cross-sectional studies

$$n = \frac{z^2pq}{d^2}$$

Where;

n = Minimum Sample size

p = 50% (as this is a pure survey)

$$q = 1 - p = 1 - 0.5 = 0.5$$

$$z = 1.96 \text{ (standard normal deviate at 95\% confidence interval)}$$

$$d = 5\% \text{ margin of error}$$

Therefore:

$$n = \frac{1.962 \times 0.5 \times 0.5}{0.052}$$

$$n = 384$$

Since our population size is a finite population (887), we therefore calculate the adjusted sample size as follows:

$$adn = n/[1 + n/N]$$

Where;

$$n = \text{Calculated sample size} = 384$$

$$N = \text{Population size} = 887$$

Therefore:

$$adn = 384/[1 + 384/887]$$

$$adn = 267.98$$

$$adn = 268$$

With a non-response rate at 10% of the adjusted sample size

$$= 10/100 \times 268 = 26.8 = 27,$$

Thus, the minimum sample size will be;

$$268 + 27 = 295.$$

The study will make a proportional allocation to the various cadres of healthcare providers of interest using the following formula

Number of workers selected per category

$$= \left(\frac{\text{Total number of workers per category}}{\text{Total number of workers}} \right) \times \text{Sample size}$$

Total number of HCWs

For Medical Doctors

$$= 277/887 \times 295 = 92.13$$

$$= 92$$

For Nurses

$$= 534/887 \times 295 = 177.59$$

$$= 177$$

For Medical Laboratory scientists

$$= 7/887 \times 295 = 2.33$$

$$= 2$$

For Pharmacists

$$= 39/887 \times 295 = 12.97$$

$$= 13$$

For Physiotherapists

$$= 17/887 \times 295 = 5.65$$

$$= 6$$

For Dieticians

$$= 8/887 \times 295 = 2.66$$

$$= 3$$

For Medical Social workers

$$= 5/887 \times 295 = 1.66$$

$$= 2$$

Accordingly, 92 Medical Doctors, 177 Nurses, 2 Medical Laboratory Scientists, 13 Pharmacists, 6 Physiotherapists, 3 Dieticians and 2 Medical social workers will be recruited.

3.7 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

Using proportional allocation, the population was divided into different categories of Healthcare workers providing clinical services to patients which include Doctors, Nurses, Medical Laboratory specialists, Pharmacists, Physiotherapists, Dieticians, and Medical Social workers. Serial enrollment will be used to recruit participants into the study till the sample size of each category is achieved.

3.8 DATA COLLECTION TOOLS

Data will be collected using a semi-structured interviewer-administered questionnaire, generally adapted from different literatures on awareness of risk factors and preventive practices against cardiovascular disease amongst healthcare workers.^{30,46} The questionnaire which is made up of four sections with 54 items will be pre-tested at St Luke's Hospital, Anua.

Section One: Socio-demographic Characteristics

This will have a total of eight (8) questions including information about the healthcare provider's age, sex, occupation, religion, marital status, highest qualification, tribe and monthly income.

Section Two: Knowledge of Healthcare workers on the risk factors of cardiovascular disease.

The twenty-eight (28) questions here will enable us to assess the awareness of cardiovascular risk factors and preventive practices against healthcare workers in the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital. This aspect of the study tool will be adopted from the Cardiovascular Disease Risk Factors Knowledge Level Scale (CARRF-KL). Respondents will report their responses on a True or False Scale. The mean will be computed and by taking this number as a cut point, the state of knowledge will be determined. A score greater than or equal to the mean will be considered a good knowledge, and less than the mean will be considered a poor knowledge.

Section Three: Preventive practices against cardiovascular disease amongst health care workers

The twelve (12) questions here will enable us to assess the preventive practices against cardiovascular diseases amongst healthcare workers. This aspect of the study tool will be adopted from a questionnaire used in a similar study (8) Respondents will make responses on a Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree.

Section Four: Factors associated with implementation of preventive practices.

This section will contain six (6) possible factors that may affect implementation of preventive practices.

3.9 STUDY VARIABLES

Independent variables:

Socio-demographic characteristics like age, sex, occupation, religion, marital status, highest qualification, tribe and monthly income.

Dependent variables:

- Awareness of cardiovascular disease risk factors
- Preventive practices against cardiovascular disease amongst health care workers.
- Factors associated with implementation of preventive practices.

3.10 DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

The questionnaires will be pretested after which corrections will be made (if need be) to ensure that the tools are valid. The questionnaires will be administered by the researchers via a face-to-face interviewing method. Each interview will last for approximately 15 minutes. A written

consent will be duly obtained via the informed consent form before the recruitment and data collection.

3.11 DATA ANALYSIS

Data will be analyzed with the use of SPSS version 20 Software. Descriptive analysis will be presented using mean and standard deviation whereas figures, text and tables will be used for data organization and presentation.

3.12 ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

Ethical approval for the study will be obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee of the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital and written consent will also be obtained from each participant. The purpose of the study will be explained to the respondents. They will be assured that no time or place will be associated with their responses and their names will not be required. They will be told that they are free to decline answering any questions that they do not feel like providing answers to. Confidentiality will be assured and ensured by not using names and other means of personal identification of participants during the research. Instead, the questionnaires will be given identification numbers. Participants will be engaged in the study in a private and convenient place within the study location. The expected duration of the interview will be 15 minutes and this will be explained to the respondents.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

4.1 INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this study was to assess the awareness of cardiovascular risk factors and preventive practices among health care workers in the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital. A total of 293 questionnaires were administered with 293 responses. This chapter represents the findings from this study.

4.2 Socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents

Table 2: Socio-demographic characteristics of the respondent (n= 293)

Variables	Sex n (%)		Total (n=293)	Statistical indices
	Male (n=82)	Female (n=211)		

Age (years)				
21-30	27 (28.4)	68 (71.6)	95 (32.4)	p value = 0.450*
31-40	34 (27.2)	91 (72.8)	125 (42.7)	
41-50	19 (33.3)	38 (66.7)	57 (19.4)	
51-60	2 (12.5)	14 (87.5)	16 (5.5)	
Mean (SD)	35.0 (7.4)	36.0 (8.1)	35.7 (7.9)	

Occupation				
Physician	52 (57.8)	38 (42.2)	90 (30.7)	P value < 0.00001+*
Nursing	15 (8.5)	162 (91.5)	177 (60.4)	
Pharmacy	10 (76.9)	3 (23.1)	13 (4.4)	
Physiotherapy	3 (50.0)	3 (50.0)	6 (2.1)	
Others	2 (28.6)	5 (71.4)	7 (2.4)	
Marital Status				
Single	40 (34.2)	77 (65.8)	117(39.9)	P value = 0.0006+*
Married	37 (22.0)	131 (78.0)	168(57.3)	
Widowed/Divorced	5 (62.5)	3 (37.5)	8 (2.7)	
Qualification				
RN	1 (3.0)	32 (97.0)	33 (11.3)	P value <0.00001+*
BSC	29 (17.7)	135 (82.3)	164 (56.0)	
MBBS	40 (52.6)	36 (47.4)	76 (25.9)	
MSc	10 (66.7)	5 (33.3)	15 (5.1)	
Others (PhD, Prof)	2 (40.0)	3 (60.0)	5 (1.7)	

Income (N)				
Less than 100,000	7 (7.8)	83 (92.2)	90 (30.7)	Df = 3
100,000 – 300,000	36 (27.7)	94 (72.3)	130 (44.4)	X ² = 43.081
300,000 – 500,000	28 (50.0)	28 (50.0)	56 (19.1)	P value <0.00001*
500,000 and above	11 (64.7)	6 (35.3)	17 (5.8)	

*Fischer's exact test; +significant P value

Table 2 shows that about 43% of the respondents are between 31 and 40 years, 60% of the respondents are nurses and 54% are married. Females are more likely to be nurses, married and earn income below N300,000.

4.3 Knowledge of Cardiovascular risk factors and preventive practices among respondents (n=293)

Table 3: Knowledge of Cardiovascular risk factors and preventive practices among respondents

Knowledge questions	Frequency	Percentage
Person always realizes if he/she has a heart disease		
True	71	24.2
False	222	75.8
Family History of CVD increases your risk of heart disease		
True	281	95.9
False	12	4.1

Elderly people are at lower risk		
True	65	22.2
False	228	77.8
Coronary Heart Disease cannot be prevented		
True	37	12.6
False	356	87.4
Smoking is not a preventable cause of death		
True	66	22.5
False	227	77.5
Smoking is a risk factor for heart disease		
True	272	92.8
False	21	7.2
The risk for heart disease increases when smoking stops		
True	47	16.0
False	246	84.0
It is harmful to eat red meat more than 3 times per week		
True	215	73.4
False	78	26.6
Eating salty food can decrease blood pressure		
True	17	5.8

False	276	94.2
Fatty meals do no increase cholesterol level		
True	19	6.5
False	274	93.5
Fats that are solid at room temperature are beneficial for heart health		
True	58	19.8
False	235	80.2
A low carbohydrate and low fat diet are beneficial for heart health		
True	272	92.8
False	21	7.2
Overweight individuals have a higher risk of heart disease		
True	271	92.5
False	22	7.2
Regular exercise reduces the risk of heart disease		
True	257	87.7
False	36	12.3
Risk can be reduced by exercising only in the gym		
True	49	16.7
	244	83.3

False		
Slow walking and wandering are also considered exercise	128	43.7
True	165	56.3
False		
Stress, sorrow and burden increase the risk of heart disease		
True	259	88.4
False	34	11.6
Blood pressure increases under stressful conditions		
True	260	88.7
False	33	11.3
High blood pressure is not a risk of heart disease		
True	99	33.7
False	193	66.3
Blood pressure control reduces the risk of heart disease		
True	265	90.4
False	28	9.6
Anti-hypertensives should be used for a lifetime		
True	222	75.8

False	71	24.2
High cholesterol increases the risk of heart disease	262	90.3
True	28	9.7
False		
There is no risk for heart disease if HDL is high	212	72.4
True	81	27.6
False		
There is no risk of heart disease if LDL is high	146	49.8
True	147	50.2
False		
Everyone with high cholesterol is given medicine		
True	125	42.7
False	168	57.3
Diabetes is a risk factor for heart disease		
True	235	80.2
False	58	19.8
The risk can be reduced in diabetic patients if glucose is controlled		
True	244	83.3
False	49	16.7

Knowledge score		Level of awareness
Below average	113	38.6
Above average	180	61.4
Average score = 21.6		

Fig 1. Level of awareness of Cardiovascular Risk Factors

Table 4: Proportion of Health workers who implement preventive practices against cardiovascular diseases

Preventive practices	Frequency	Percentage
Exercise	246	84.0
Fat diet	169	57.7
Adequate sleep	203	69.3
Salt reduction	167	57.0
Regular Blood pressure check	185	63.1
Regular Blood sugar check	136	46.4
Maintaining BMI	153	52.2

Other activities	94	32.1
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Fig 2. Level of Implementation of preventive practices among healthcare workers.

Table 5: Exercise activities among the correspondents

Variables	Frequency (n=293)	Percentage
Type of exercise		
Jogging	142	48.5
Swimming	25	8.3
Weight lifting	12	4.1
Brisk walking	184	62.8
Others		

How long in a day		
Less than 30 min	119	40.6
30 min to 1 hour	140	47.8
Greater than 1 hour	31	10.6
Greater than 5 hours	3	1.0
How many times in a week		
Once	93	31.7
Twice	112	38.2
Five	81	27.6
More than 5 times	7	2.4

Though 84% of the participants engaged in exercise only 30% regularly exercise at least five times a week.

Table 6: Alcohol intake among the correspondents

Variables	Frequency (n=293)	Percentage
Do you take alcohol		
Yes	61	20.8
No	232	79.2

How long in a day		
Beer	27	44.3
Wine	29	47.5
Spirit	3	4.9
Others	2	3.3
How many bottles	(n = 61)	
Less than 5	49	80.3
5 to 10	11	18.0
Above 10	1	1.6

This table shows that only 20.8% of the health workers consume alcohol, in 47.5% of cases its only wine, majority of them (80%) consume less than 5 bottles

Table 7: Smoking pattern of the respondents

Variables	Frequency (n=293)	Percentage
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Do you smoke?		
Yes	11	3.8
No	282	96.2
How long (years)	(n = 11)	
Less than 5	7	63.6
5 - 10	3	27.3
Above 10	1	9.1
How many sticks per day	(n = 11)	
Less than 10 sticks	8	72.7
10 - 20 sticks	3	27.3

The table shows only 3.8% (11/293) smoke cigarettes, 64% have smoked for less than 5 years

Table 8: Work pattern of the respondents

Work Pattern	Frequency (n=293)	Percentage
How many hours do you work in a day?		
4 – 8 hours	168	57.3
More than 8 hours	125	42.7
How many days in a week	(n = 11)	
Less than 3 days	3	1.0
3 – 5 days	227	77.5
More than 5 days	63	21.5

How do you cope with stress		
Sleep	293	100.0
How many hours do you sleep		
Less than 4 hours	8	2.7
4 – 6 hours	194	66.2
More than 6 hours	91	31.1

The table shows that 42.8% work more than 8 hours per day and 77.5% work for 3 to 5 days in a week, only 315 sleep more than 6 hours per day

Table 9: Dietary pattern of the respondents

Diet	Frequency (n=293)	Percentage
How often do you take fruits and vegetables		
Less than once a week	40	13.7
Once a week	83	28.3
Twice a week	93	31.7
Thrice a week	77	26.3
Do you add salt to your food after cooking?		
Yes	32	10.9
No	261	89.1

How often do you take butter or fatty meals?	(n = 11)	
Everyday	3	1.0
Occasionally	102	35.8
Rarely	185	63.1

This table shows that 26% eat fruits/vegetables up to thrice a week, 13.8% do not take fruit every week. About 11% add salt to the food after cooking, 63.1% claimed they rarely take butter.

Table 10: Secondary prevention for hypertension and diabetes mellitus among the respondents

Variables	Frequency (n=293)	Percentage
Have you ever checked your BP?		
Yes	264	90.1
No	29	9.9
How often do you check your BP?	(n = 264)	
Monthly	178	67.4
Every 6 months	61	23.1
Yearly	25	9.5
What was the last systolic value?	(n = 264)	
Less than 120	135	51.1
120-129	54	20.5
	63	23.9

130-139	12	4.6
140 and above		
What was the last diastolic value	(n = 11)	
Less than 80	183	69.3
80-89	49	18.6
90 and above	32	12.1
Ever diagnosed hypertensive?		
Yes	16	6.1
No	248	93.9
How long ago were you diagnosed with hypertension?	(n=16)	
Less than 10 years	14	87.5
10 – 20 years	1	6.2
Above 20 years	1	6.2
How often do you take your medication?		
Everyday	14	87.5
Weekly	2	12.5
How often do you check your blood sugar		
Weekly	3	1.0
Monthly	148	50.5
Rarely	142	48.5
Ever diagnosed with diabetes?		

Yes	1	0.3
No	292	99.7

The table shows that 90% of the health workers have checked their blood pressure before, 675 check their blood pressure every month. Based on the last measurement 55 of them have high systolic and 12% have high diastolic blood pressure. 6% of the health workers have been diagnosed hypertensive. Only 0.3% have been diagnosed diabetic, 50.55 carry out monthly sugar check.

Note: Good practice is defined as respondent with regular exercise (exercise more than 30 minutes per day and at least five times a week), adequate sleep more than 6 hours a day and not a smoker. From our analysis, 44 participants out of 293 had met the criteria for good practice (15% of the total population of health workers)

Table 11: Socio-demographic factors associated with good preventive practices

Variables	Frequency (n=293)		Statistical indices
	Good (n = 44)	Poor (n = 249)	
Age (years)			
21 – 30	16	79 (83.2)	P value = 0.202* Df = 291 Tt = 2.118
31 – 40	22	103 (82.4)	
41 – 50	6	51 (89.5)	
51 – 60	0	16 (100.0)	

Mean (SD)	33.4 (6.3)	36.1 (8.1)	P value = 0.035+
Sex			Df = 1
Male	19 (23.2)	63 (76.8)	X ² = 5.932
Female	25 (11.9)	18 (88.1)	P value = 0.015+
Occupation			
Physician	32 (35.6)	58 (64.4)	P value <0.0001+
Nursing	7 (4.0)	170 (96.0)	
Pharmacy	2 (15.4)	11 (84.6)	
Physiotherapy	1 (16.7)	5 (83.3)	
Others	2 (28.6)	5 (71.4)	
Marital status			
Single	22 (18.8)	95 (81.2)	P value = 0.26*
Married	22 (13.1)	146 (86.9)	
Widowed/Divorced	0 (0.0)	8 (100.0)	
Income (N)			
Less than 100,000	7 (7.8)	83 (92.2)	Df = 3
1000,000 – 300,000	16 (12.3)	114 (87.7)	X ² = 15.266
300,000 – 500,000	16 (28.6)	40 (71.4)	P value = 0.002+
500,000 and above	5 (29.4)	12 (70.60)	
Tribe			
Ibibio	23 (14.2)	139 (85.8)	
Anang	9 (14.5)	53 (85.5)	
Oron	7 (21.2)	26 (78.8)	P value = 0.146*
Igbo	1 (4.2)	23 (95.8)	
Yoruba	3 (42.9)	4 (57.1)	
Others	1 (20.0)	4 (80.0)	

Knowledge score			Df = 1
Below average	20 (17.7)	93 (82.3)	X ² = 1.037
Above average	24 (13.3)	156 (86.7)	P value = 0.309
Average score = 21.6			

*Fischer's exact test; + significant P value

The table shows that the respondents with good preventive practices are significantly lower than those who are not (15%), though the age groups for both groups are similar, male sex are more likely to have good preventive practice, same with physicians and high income earners.

Table 12: Factors associated with the implementation of preventive practices for cardiovascular disease among the respondents

	Agree	Neutral	Disagree
Engaging in exercise			
Time	221 (75.4)	23 (7.9)	49 (16.7)
Cost	168 (57.3)	50 (17.1)	75 (25.6)
Lack of Knowledge	178 (59.7)	55 (18.8)	63 (21.5)
Inexperience	161 (54.9)	48 (16.4)	84 (28.7)
Maintaining Healthy weight			
Time	139 (47.4)	56 (19.1)	98 (33.5)
Cost	184 (62.8)	40 (13.7)	69 (23.6)
Previous unsuccessful experience	211 (72.3)	26 (8.9)	55 (18.8)
Lack of knowledge	165 (56.4)	47 (16.0)	81 (27.6)

Eating low fat			
Taste	123 (42.0)	71 (24.2)	99 (33.8)
Time	121 (41.3)	49 (16.7)	123 (42.0)
Cost	170 (58.0)	56 (19.1)	67 (22.9)
Availability	161 (55.0)	46 (15.7)	86 (29.3)
Smoking cessation			
Previous unsuccessful experience	195 (66.5)	38 (13.0)	60 (20.5)
	209 (71.3)	32 (10.9)	52 (17.8)
Lack of support	164 (56.2)	47 (16.1)	81 (27.7)
Lack of knowledge			
Alcohol reduction			
Previous unsuccessful experience	218 (74.4)	29 (9.9)	46 (15.7)
	180 (61.4)	62 (21.2)	51 (17.4)
Lack of support	168 (57.3)	47 (16.1)	78 (26.6)
Lack of knowledge			
Managing stress			
Long working hours	201 (68.6)	33 (11.3)	59 (20.1)
Financial gain	148 (50.5)	67 (22.9)	78 (26.6)
Lack of knowledge	182 (61.8)	57 (19.4)	55 (18.8)

Fig 3. Factors associated with implementation of preventive practices as perceived by health workers in UUTH.

Majority of respondents admitted to lack of time being the commonest factor associated with not engaging in exercise (75.4%). For healthy weight and alcohol reduction, previous unsuccessful experience was the most common factor (72.3% and 74.4% respectively). Cost (62.8%) was the most important factor influencing choice of low fat diet while smoking cessation was most influenced by lack of support. For managing stress, long working hours is the most important factor.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION

5.1 Introduction

This study was carried out among health care workers in the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital. A total of 293 health workers consisting of 28% males and 72% females. The majority of the population were Ibibios (55.2%) while the highest population of healthcare workers were nurses (60.4%) followed by doctors (30.7%). Medical social workers constituted the least population of health workers in this study (0.003%). A similar study done in Bowen University amongst 324 health workers consisted of 44.1% males and 55.9% females. Of this population, there were also more nurses than doctors comprising 25% and 5.6% of the total population respectively.⁴⁷

5.2 Awareness of Risk factors of Cardiovascular Diseases

From our study only 38.6% of participants had below average knowledge of cardiovascular risk factors with hypertension, smoking, dyslipidemia, obesity, physical inactivity, unhealthy diet and diabetes being correctly identified as CVD risk factors in 66.3%, 92.8% 90.35, 92.55, 87.7%, 92.8%, 80.2% respectively. A study among healthcare workers in Saudi Arabia revealed that 55.8% of respondents had strong knowledge of CVD, while 44.2% had inadequate awareness of CVD risk factors and preventive method.⁴⁸ In Enugu, a similar study showed that an average of 95.5% of the participants correctly identified hypertension, smoking, dyslipidemia, obesity, physical inactivity and diabetes as CVD risk factors.⁴⁹ Study done also among the staff of Ekiti State University shows that low knowledge of heart disease risk factors was found in 68.6% of the respondents.⁵⁰

5.3 Preventive Practices among Health workers

Our study showed that 15% of participants had good preventive practices. 30% of participants exercise at least 5 times per week, 26% eat fruits and vegetables up to three times a week while 89.1% do not add salt to their food after cooking. Compared to other professionals, doctors were observed to have the highest percentage (35%) of healthcare workers with good preventive practices. In a study among health workers in the University of Port-Harcourt Teaching Hospital, 98.5% of health workers showed poor compliance with cardiovascular disease preventive measures.³⁵

5.4 Factors associated with implementation of preventive practices among healthcare workers

Our study shows no significant association between age of the participants and the implementation of preventive practices though participants above 40 years were the most unlikely to be involved in good practices (89.5%). Male participants had a high likelihood of implementing good preventive practices (23.2%) when compared to their female counterparts (11.9%). Also, more physicians (35%) admitted to engaging in good preventive practices compared to other healthcare professionals: Nurses (4%), Pharmacists (15.4%), physiotherapists (16.7%) and others (28%). Individuals with income more than 300,000 (28.7%) are twice more likely to be involved in good practices as compared to those with lower income (10.4%).

Our study further probed the factors influencing the implementation of preventive practices as perceived by the participants. Majority of respondents admitted to lack of time being the most common factor associated with not engaging in exercise (75.4%). For healthy weight and alcohol reduction, previous unsuccessful experience was the most common factor (72.3% and 74.4% respectively). Cost (62.8%) was the most important factor influencing choice of

low fat diet while smoking cessation was most influenced by lack of support (71.3%). For managing stress, long working hours was the most important factor.

CHAPTER SIX

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

6.1 Conclusion

The study revealed that 61.4% of participants have above average level of awareness of cardiovascular risk factors. Of the 293 participants, 15% are engaged in good preventive practices. There is no significant association between awareness of risk factors and implementation of preventive practices. Although the participants have a good level of awareness of cardiovascular risk factors, there is no significant association with good preventive practice. Factors associated with implementation of good factors include: male sex, higher level of income, physicians.

6.2 Limitations

1. Funding was a limitation as this study was done purely out of pocket.
2. Difficulty in accessing some existing literature.

6.3 Recommendations

1. The Chief Medical Director of the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital should include lectures on the need for implementation of preventive practices against cardiovascular diseases.
2. The Chief Medical Director of University of Uyo Teaching Hospital should include weekly exercise sessions in the hospital calendar to encourage workers to exercise regularly.
3. The Federal Government should employ more staff to reduce working hour and workplace stress.
4. Further studies should be done to confirm these findings and shed more light on specific professionals.

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